

Estimating Zero-Crossings of Uniformly Sampled Data

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Abstract

Analysis of the zero-crossing times of angle-modulated signals provides a computationally efficient means of implementing a number of processing functions, including demodulation and spectral estimation. Unfortunately, sampling of a bandlimited signal is typically accomplished using uniformly spaced amplitude samples rather than detecting the zero-crossing times. This paper investigates the use of linear interpolation to estimate zero-crossing times from the uniformly-sampled data. The statistical properties of the error due to interpolation, additive Gaussian noise and quantization are each considered separately as a function of the sampling interval.

1 Introduction

Zero-crossing-based processing of angle-modulated waveforms has been implemented with promising results for processes ranging from spectral estimation and signal discrimination to FM signal detection and instantaneous frequency measurement [7], [6], [2], [5]. A practical problem in implementing these techniques is that, in a typical application, the sampled data is at uniformly spaced intervals (e.g. Nyquist sampling), not at detected zero-crossings. Techniques for increasing the sampling rate with the use of frequency domain zero-padding [1, 637] or with finite impulse response (FIR) filters [4] provide a means of getting 'closer' to the true zero-crossing, but some type of estimate is still needed to determine the zero-crossing time.

One method of estimating the zero-crossing times is to interpolate between samples. Because of its' computational simplicity, this paper examines the suitability of a linear interpolation. Other methods of interpolation could be implemented using higher degree Lagrange interpolating polynomials, however, the number of calculations required for even a second-order approximation is significantly more than the simple linear approximation. Because the calculation is required at each zero-crossing, these methods are not pursued here.

Therefore, we will assume the zero-crossing times will be approximated from a linear interpolation between data samples of opposite sign. Let $(x(t_1), t_1)$ and $(x(t_2), t_2)$

Figure 1: Linear Interpolation Between Samples of a Sinusoid.

represent two successive data samples of a waveform $x(t)$ for which $\text{sign}(x(t_1)) = -\text{sign}(x(t_2))$. A line between these points satisfies the equation

$$x(t) = \frac{t - t_2}{t_1 - t_2} x(t_1) + \frac{t - t_1}{t_2 - t_1} x(t_2)$$

Setting $x(t) = 0$ and solving for the estimated zero-crossing time, \hat{t}_{c_1} , yields

$$\hat{t}_{c_1} = t_1 - x(t_1) \cdot \frac{T_s}{x(t_2) - x(t_1)} \quad (1)$$

where $T_s = t_2 - t_1$, and T_s is the sampling interval (assumed constant). Figure 1 illustrates these parameters for the case when $x(t)$ is a sinusoid.

2 Error Analysis

This section provides an analysis of the effect of various sources of errors on the approximation of the zero-crossing times using Equation 1. It is assumed the sampled signal is a sinusoid as described by

$$x(t) = A \sin(\omega_0 t + \phi_0) \quad (2)$$

Without loss of generality, we can assume $A = 1$ and $\phi_0 = 0$. In applying these results to a more general

bandlimited sampled signal with a highest frequency of $f_o (= 1/T_o)$, then since $T_s \leq T_o/2$, it is still reasonable to assume the signal is approximately sinusoidal between successive samples. In addition, it is convenient to analyze the first zero-crossing (as shown in Figure 1). Since the process can be assumed time-invariant, the results that follow are applicable to any zero-crossing event estimate.

The three principle sources of errors in zero-crossing estimates investigated here are the error due to linear interpolation, the error due to additive noise, and the error due to quantization. Each case is handled separately in the following sections. For each error type, we derive an expression for the mean and variance of the error in the estimate.

2.1 Effect of Linear Interpolation

In this section, we investigate the mean and variance of the error due to the linear interpolation. First, consider the zero-crossing interval between points t_1 and t_2 , as shown in the Figure 1, in which t_1 and t_2 are defined such that they are of different sign and there are no other sample points between them. For a given sample period, T_s , then t_2 could alternatively be defined as

$$t_2 = t_1 + T_s$$

Note the *true* zero-crossing time, denoted by t_c , must occur between these two sample points. From Equations 1 and 2, the estimated zero-crossing time, \hat{t}_c , is then computed as

$$\hat{t}_c = t_1 - \sin(\omega_o t_1) \cdot \frac{T_s}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) - \sin(\omega_o t_1)}$$

The error, ϵ , is then computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= t_c - \hat{t}_c \\ &= t_c - t_1 + \frac{T_s \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) - \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For the case of sampling at the Nyquist rate, then T_s can be expressed in terms of the signal period, T_o , as $T_s = T_o/2 = \pi/\omega_o$. Substituting this value for T_s , Equation 3 simplifies to

$$\epsilon = t_c - t_1 - \frac{T_o}{4}$$

With the assumption that the initial phase, ϕ_o , is zero, the first zero-crossing occurs at $t_c = T_o/2$ and the error is simply

$$\epsilon = t_c - t_1 - T_o/4 = T_o/4 - t_1$$

As would be expected, the error is zero for $t_1 = T_o/4$ (when the linear interpolation is symmetric about the true zero-crossing point). The mean error, $\bar{\epsilon}$, is found by computing

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon} &= E[\epsilon] \\ &= T_o/4 - E[t_1] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $E[\cdot]$ is the expectation operator defined as

$$E[g(x)] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) p_x(x) dx \quad (5)$$

with $p_x(x)$ the probability density function of a continuous random variable, x , and $g(x)$ a continuous measurable function of x . Assuming the sample point, t_1 , is equally likely to occur at any point over the interval $t_c - T_s < t_1 < t_c$, then t_1 can be modeled as a uniform random variable with a probability density function defined as

$$p(t_1) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{T_s} & \text{for } t_c - T_s \leq t_1 < t_c \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The mean error is then

$$\bar{\epsilon} = T_o/4 - \int_{t_c - T_s}^{t_c} t_1 \cdot \frac{1}{T_s} dt_1$$

Replacing T_s with $T_o/2$ for Nyquist rate sampling, the mean error is found to be

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon} &= T_o/4 - 2/T_o \cdot \int_0^{T_o/2} t_1 dt_1 \\ &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The variance of the error, denoted by $\text{var}(\epsilon)$, is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) &= E[\epsilon^2] - E^2[\epsilon] \\ &= E[(T_o/4 - t_1)^2] \\ &= E[T_o^2/16 - T_o/2 \cdot t_1 + t_1^2] \\ &= T_o^2/16 - T_o/2 \cdot E[t_1] + E[t_1^2] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

From Equations 4 and 7

$$E[t_1] = T_o/4 \quad (10)$$

Using Equation 5, the last term is

$$\begin{aligned} E[t_1^2] &= 2/T_o \cdot \int_0^{T_o/2} t_1^2 dt_1 \\ &= T_o^2/12 \end{aligned}$$

From Equations 9 and 10, the variance of the error is then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) &= T_o^2/16 - T_o/2 \cdot T_o/4 + T_o^2/12 \\ &= T_o^2/48 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

A more difficult calculation is for the general case of sampling at a rate equal to or greater than the Nyquist rate in which case $T_s \leq T_o/2$. T_s is not considered a random variable, but a parameter which, for a given process, is fixed.

Equation 3 can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon &= t_c - t_1 + \frac{T_s \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{2 \cos(1/2(2\omega_o t_1 + \omega_o T_s)) \sin(1/2(\omega_o T_s))} \\ &= t_c - t_1 + \frac{T_s}{2 \sin(\omega_o T_s/2)} \cdot \frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{\cos(\omega_o t_1 + \omega_o(T_s/2))}\end{aligned}$$

and, after further manipulation, as

$$\epsilon = t_c - t_1 + \frac{T_s}{2 \sin(\omega_o T_s/2)} \cdot \frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{\cos(\omega_o t_1) \cos(\omega_o(T_s/2)) - \sin(\omega_o t_1) \sin(\omega_o(T_s/2))}$$

To simplify the expression, define the following constants as

$$\begin{aligned}a &= \cos(\omega_o T_s/2) \\ b &= \sin(\omega_o T_s/2)\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

then the error can be expressed as

$$\epsilon = t_c - t_1 + \frac{T_s}{2b} \cdot \frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \quad (13)$$

And the mean error is then

$$\bar{\epsilon} = t_c - E[t_1] + \frac{T_s}{2b} \cdot E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right]$$

With $t_c = T_o/2$ (for the case of the first zero-crossing and zero initial phase), then

$$E[t_1] = \frac{T_o - T_s}{2} \quad (14)$$

Note, for $T_s = T_o/2$, the expected value of t_1 is the same as that of Equation 10. Now, computing the term

$$E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = \int_{T_o/2 - T_s}^{T_o/2} \frac{1}{T_s} \frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} dt_1$$

The integral can be evaluated as

$$E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = \left. \frac{[-b\omega_o t_1 - a \ln(-b \sin(\omega_o t_1) + a \cos(\omega_o t_1))]}{T_s \omega_o \cdot (a^2 + b^2)} \right|_{T_o/2 - T_s}^{T_o/2}$$

If we let $a^2 + b^2 = 1$, evaluate over the limits, and simplify, the expected value reduces to

$$E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = \frac{a \ln(-a) + b\omega_o T_s - a \ln(-a \cos(\omega_o T_s) - b \sin(\omega_o T_s))}{T_s \omega_o}$$

Substituting for a and b from Equation 12, it can be shown the previous equation can be expressed as

$$E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = -\sin \left(\frac{\omega_o T_s}{2} \right) = -b \quad (15)$$

Combining the results from Equations 14 and 15,

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\epsilon} &= t_c - \frac{T_o - T_s}{2} + \frac{T_s}{2b} \cdot -b \\ &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

Therefore, even in the general case, the mean error is zero.

The next step is to calculate a general expression for the variance of the error as a function of the sampling period, T_s . From Equations 8, 13 and 16, and replacing t_c with $T_o/2$, then the variance of the error is

$$\begin{aligned}\text{var}(\epsilon) &= E \left[\left(\frac{T_o}{2} - t_1 + \frac{T_s}{2b} \frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right)^2 \right] \\ &= T_o^2/4 - T_o E[t_1] + E[t_1^2] \\ &\quad + \frac{T_s^2}{4b^2} \cdot E \left[\frac{\sin^2(\omega_o t_1)}{(a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1))^2} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{T_o T_s}{2b} \cdot E \left[\frac{\sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{T_s}{b} \cdot E \left[\frac{t_1 \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right]\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

The term $E[t_1^2]$ is found to be

$$E[t_1^2] = \frac{T_o^2}{4} - \frac{T_o T_s}{2} + \frac{T_s^2}{3} \quad (18)$$

The term $E \left[\frac{\sin^2(\omega_o t_1)}{(a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1))^2} \right]$ is evaluated using the following integral [3, 184]

$$\begin{aligned}\int \frac{A_1 \cos^2 x + 2A_2 \sin x \cos x + A_3 \sin^2 x}{B_1 \cos^2 x + 2B_2 \sin x \cos x + B_3 \sin^2 x} dx = \\ \frac{1}{4B_2^2 + (B_1 - B_3)^2} \cdot \{ [4A_2 B_2 + (A_1 - A_3)(B_1 - B_3)] \cdot x \\ + [(A_1 - A_3)B_2 - A_2(B_1 - B_3)] \\ \cdot \ln(B_1 \cos^2 x + 2B_2 \sin x \cos x + B_3 \sin^2 x) \\ + [2(A_1 + A_3)B_2^2 - 2A_2 B_2(B_1 + B_3) \\ + (B_1 A_3 - A_1 B_3)(B_1 - B_3)] \cdot (-1/(B_3 \tan x + B_2)) \}\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

Applying Equation 19, evaluating over the limits, and simplifying results in

$$E \left[\frac{\sin^2(\omega_o t_1)}{(a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1))^2} \right] = \frac{\cos \omega_o T_s + \sin \omega_o T_s}{\omega_o T_s} \quad (20)$$

And, last, calculating the final unknown term as given by

$$E \left[\frac{t_1 \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{T_s} \cdot \int_{T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} \frac{t_1 \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} dt_1 \\
&= \frac{1}{T_s} \cdot \int_{T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} \frac{t_1}{a \cot(\omega_o t_1) - b} dt_1
\end{aligned}$$

Integrating by parts with

$$\int U dv = UV - \int V du \quad (21)$$

and U and V defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
U &= t_1 \\
dU &= dt_1 \\
dV &= \frac{1}{a \cot \omega_o t_1 - b} dt_1 \\
V &= \int \frac{1}{a \cot \omega_o t_1 - b} dt_1
\end{aligned}$$

then, solving for V yields,

$$V = -bt_1 - \frac{a}{\omega_o} \ln(-b \sin \omega_o t_1 + a \cos \omega_o t_1)$$

And, applying Equation 21,

$$\begin{aligned}
&E \left[\frac{t_1 \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = \\
&\frac{1}{T_s} \cdot \left[\left(-bt_1^2 - \frac{at_1}{\omega_o} \ln(-b \sin \omega_o t_1 + a \cos \omega_o t_1) \right) \Big|_{t_1=T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} bt_1 + \frac{a}{\omega_o} \ln(-b \sin \omega_o t_1 + a \cos \omega_o t_1) dt_1 \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{T_s} \cdot \left[\frac{a\pi}{\omega_o^2} \cdot \left(-\ln \frac{a}{a \cos \omega_o T_s + b \sin \omega_o T_s} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{b}{2} (T_s^2 - T_o T_s) - \frac{a T_s}{\omega_o} \cdot \ln(-b \sin \omega_o T_s - a \sin \omega_o T_s) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} \frac{a}{\omega_o} \ln(-b \sin \omega_o t_1 + a \cos \omega_o t_1) dt_1 \right]
\end{aligned}$$

From [3, 251]

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_0^x \ln(\alpha \cos x - \beta \sin x) dx = x \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + \beta^2}}{2} \right) \\
&+ \frac{1}{2i} [Li_2(-e^{2i(\phi-x)}) - Li_2(-e^{2i\phi})] - x(x-2\phi) \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
i &= \sqrt{-1} \\
\tan \phi &= -\frac{\beta}{\alpha} \\
|\phi| &\leq \frac{\pi}{2} \\
|\phi - x| &\leq \frac{\pi}{2} \\
Li_2(x) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{k^2}
\end{aligned}$$

And, in addition, for $x_2 > x_1$

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} g(x) dx = \int_0^{x_2} g(x) dx - \int_0^{x_1} g(x) dx$$

Therefore, using Equation 22 and simplifying,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{T_o/2-T_s}^{T_o/2} \frac{a}{\omega_o} \ln(-b \sin \omega_o t_1 + a \cos \omega_o t_1) dt_1 = \\
&\frac{a}{\omega_o^2} \cdot \left\{ \omega_o T_s \ln \frac{1}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} \cdot \sin(k\omega_o T_s) - \omega_o^2 T_s T_o \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

Combining these results and simplifying

$$\begin{aligned}
&E \left[\frac{t_1 \sin(\omega_o t_1)}{a \cos(\omega_o t_1) - b \sin(\omega_o t_1)} \right] = \\
&\frac{1}{T_s} \cdot \left\{ -\frac{a}{\omega_o} (\ln a + T_s \ln 2) + \frac{T_s^2 b}{2} - T_o T_s (a + b/2) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{a}{\omega_o^2} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} \cdot \sin(k\omega_o T_s) \right) \right\} \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

And, finally, combining the intermediate results of Equations 14, 15, 18, 20 and 23 and simplifying yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{var}(\epsilon) &= -\frac{T_s^2}{6} + \frac{T_s}{4b^2\omega_o} (\cos \omega_o T_s + \sin \omega_o T_s) \\
&+ \frac{a}{b} \left\{ \frac{\ln a + T_s \ln 2}{\omega_o} + T_o T_s - \frac{1}{\omega_o^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin(k\omega_o T_s)}{k^2} \right\} \quad (24)
\end{aligned}$$

Unfortunately, Equation 24 doesn't provide a very illuminating measure of the variance for the general sampling rate. It may be more practical to use the result of Equation 11, sampling at the Nyquist rate, as an estimate of the error variance due to linear interpolation.

2.2 Effect of Additive White Gaussian Noise

The next error considered is that due to additive white Gaussian noise. With reference to Figure 2, the following assumptions will be made initially

1. The first sample occurs at time t_1 and is assumed to occur within the bounds $t_c - T_s \leq t_1 < t_c$, where t_c is the true zero-crossing time.
2. The second sample, t_2 , occurs T_s seconds after t_1 and a zero-crossing occurs between t_1 and t_2 .
3. The noise at time t_1 (denoted by n_1) and at t_2 (denoted by n_2) is zero-mean AWGN of variance σ^2 .
4. t_1 is assumed to be a uniformly distributed random variable as described by Equation 6.
5. t_1 , n_1 and n_2 are statistically independent.

Figure 2: Effect of AWGN on Zero-Crossing Estimates

The signal to be sampled is modeled as a stationary random process given by

$$x(t) = \sin \omega_o t + n(t)$$

where $n(t)$ refers to the AWGN random process. From Equation 1, the estimated zero-crossing time is then

$$\hat{t}_c = t_1 - \frac{T_s(\sin(\omega_o t_1) + n(t_1))}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) + n(t_2) - \sin(\omega_o t_1) - n(t_1)}$$

And the error is then calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= t_c - \hat{t}_c \\ &= \frac{T_o}{2} - t_1 + \frac{T_s(\sin(\omega_o t_1) + n_1)}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) + n_2 - \sin(\omega_o t_1) - n_1} \end{aligned}$$

which represents the general form of the error. Note, it implicitly includes both the error due to noise and also due to linear interpolation. The expected error is

$$\begin{aligned} E[\epsilon] &= T_o/2 - \frac{T_o - T_s}{2} \\ &+ T_s \cdot E \left[\frac{\sin \omega_o t_1}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) - \sin \omega_o t_1 + n_2 - n_1} \right] \\ &+ T_s \cdot E \left[\frac{n_1}{\sin(\omega_o(t_1 + T_s)) - \sin \omega_o t_1 + n_2 - n_1} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Unfortunately, a closed solution to Equation 25 becomes intractable and, therefore, additional assumptions must be made. First, it is necessary to assume t_1 is not a random variable, but fixed and defined as

$$\begin{aligned} t_1 &= t_c - \frac{T_s}{2} \\ &= \frac{T_o - T_s}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

With this assumption, t_1 and t_2 are defined such that they are symmetric across the true zero-crossing, $t_c = T_o/2$. For this case, the error due to the linear interpolation is zero as shown by substituting this value of t_1 into Equation 3. This assumption effectively narrows the focus of the analysis to only the effect of the AWGN as a function

of the noise statistics and the sampling period. Substituting for t_1 and with $b = \sin(\omega_o T_s/2)$, Equation 25 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} E[\epsilon] &= \frac{T_s}{2} + T_s \cdot \left\{ E \left[\frac{b}{-2b + n_2 - n_1} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + E \left[\frac{n_1}{-2b + n_2 - n_1} \right] \right\} \end{aligned}$$

With $T_s < T_o/2$, and if the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and T_s are sufficiently large (such that $\omega_o T_s/2$ does not approach zero), it can also be assumed that

$$|b| = \left| \sin \frac{\omega_o T_s}{2} \right| \gg n_1, n_2$$

Therefore

$$-2b + n_2 - n_1 \approx -2b \quad (27)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} E[\epsilon] &\approx \frac{T_s}{2} + T_s \cdot \left\{ E \left[\frac{b}{-2b} \right] + \frac{E[n_1]}{-2b} \right\} \\ &\approx \frac{T_s}{2} - T_s \cdot \frac{1}{2} \\ &\approx 0 \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

The variance of the zero-crossing estimate error due to AWGN is computed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) &= E \left[\left(\frac{T_s}{2} + \frac{T_s}{-2b + n_2 - n_1} \cdot (b + n_1) \right)^2 \right] \\ &= T_s^2 \cdot E \left[\frac{1}{4} + \frac{(b + n_1)^2}{(-2b + n_2 - n_1)^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{b + n_1}{-2b + n_2 - n_1} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Using the approximation of Equation 27 then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) &\approx T_s^2 \cdot E \left[\frac{1}{4} + \frac{(b + n_1)^2}{4b^2} + \frac{b + n_1}{-2b} \right] \\ &\approx \frac{T_s^2 \sigma^2}{4 \sin^2(\omega_o T_s/2)} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Note the approximation of the variance is proportional to the noise power, σ^2 , and the square of the sampling period, T_s . As either of these two parameters approach zero, the variance of the error also approaches zero.

2.3 Effect of Quantization

Last, an analysis is made on the effect of sample quantization on the estimation of zero crossing times. Since quantization is, in general, a non-linear process, it is necessary to make some assumptions to obtain a reasonable model of the process. In this case, the assumptions are the same as those made for AWGN except the quantization is modeled as additive noise with a uniform distribution. The probability density function of the additive quantization noise, g , is given by

$$p_Q(g) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{q_o} & \text{for } -\frac{q_o}{2} \leq g < \frac{q_o}{2} \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere} \end{cases}$$

Figure 3: Effect of Quantization on Zero-Crossing Estimates

where q_o is the quantization step size relative to a unit amplitude sinusoid (e.g., $A = 1$ in Equation 2, otherwise q_o must be normalized by dividing by A). To make the computation tractable and eliminate the linear interpolation error from the computation, it is also necessary to make the assumption of Equation 26 used in computing the AWGN effect. Figure 3 illustrates the model being used.

With these assumptions, the error can be expressed using Equation 25 and 26 and substituting q_1 and q_2 for n_1 and n_2 , where q_j represents the additive error at time t_j .

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= t_c - \hat{t}_c \\ &= \frac{T_o}{2} - t_1 + \frac{T_s (\sin(\omega_o t_1) + q_1)}{\sin(\omega_o t_2) + q_2 - \sin(\omega_o t_1) - q_1} \\ &= \frac{T_s}{2} + T_s \cdot \frac{b + q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The final result above obtained by substituting $b = \sin(\omega_o T_s/2)$, $t_1 = T_o/2 - T_s/2$, and $t_2 = t_1 + T_s$. The expected error is

$$E[\epsilon] = \frac{T_s}{2} + T_s \cdot \left\{ E \left[\frac{b}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] + E \left[\frac{q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] \right\} \quad (31)$$

Computing the first term

$$E \left[\frac{b}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] = \int \int_{-q_o/2}^{q_o/2} \frac{1}{q_o^2} \cdot \frac{b}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} dq_1 dq_2$$

then, after integrating and simplifying, the result is

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{b}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] &= \frac{b}{q_o^2} \cdot \{4b \ln(-2b) \\ &- (q_o + 2b) \ln(-(q_o + 2b)) + (q_o - 2b) \ln(q_o - 2b)\} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Computing the second term

$$E \left[\frac{q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] = \int \int_{-q_o/2}^{q_o/2} \frac{1}{q_o^2} \cdot \frac{q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} dq_1 dq_2$$

Again, after integrating and simplifying, the result is

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right] &= \frac{b}{q_o^2} \cdot \left\{ -4b \ln(-2b) - \frac{q_o^2}{2b} \right. \\ &- (q_o - 2b) \ln(-2b + q_o) + (q_o + 2b) \ln(-(2b + q_o)) \} \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Combining the results of Equations 32 and 33 yields

$$\begin{aligned} E[\epsilon] &= \frac{T_s}{2} + T_s \cdot \left\{ \frac{b}{q_o^2} \cdot \{4 \ln(-2b) \right. \\ &- (q_o + 2b) \ln(-(q_o + 2b)) + (q_o - 2b) \ln(q_o - 2b)\} \\ &+ \frac{b}{q_o^2} \cdot \{ -4b \ln(-2b) - (q_o - 2b) \ln(-2b + q_o) \\ &+ (q_o + 2b) \ln(-(2b + q_o)) - \frac{q_o^2}{2b} \} \} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Therefore, as would be expected, the mean error due to quantization is zero.

The final step is the computation of the variance of the error due to quantization. With the error as defined by Equation 30, the mean error equal to zero, and using the result of Equation 31, then the variance is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) &= E[\epsilon^2] \\ &= T_s^2 \cdot E \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{b + q_1}{-2b + q_2 - q_1} \right)^2 \right] \\ &= T_s^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{2} + E \left[\frac{b^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + E \left[\frac{2bq_1}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] + E \left[\frac{q_1^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] \right) \end{aligned}$$

Computing the first unknown term

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{b^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] &= \\ &\int \int_{-q_o/2}^{q_o/2} \frac{1}{q_o^2} \cdot \frac{b^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} dq_1 dq_2 \end{aligned}$$

Integrating and simplifying results in

$$E \left[\frac{b^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] = \frac{1}{q_o^2} \cdot b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_o^2} \right) \quad (35)$$

Computing the second unknown term

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{2bq_1}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] &= \\ &\frac{2b}{q_o^2} \int \int_{-q_o/2}^{q_o/2} \frac{q_1}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} dq_1 dq_2 \end{aligned}$$

Integrating and simplifying results in

$$\begin{aligned} E \left[\frac{2bq_1}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] &= \\ &\frac{1}{q_o^2} \left\{ -q_o b \ln \left(\frac{2b - q_o}{2b + q_o} \right) - 4b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_o^2} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

And, last, computing the third unknown term

$$E \left[\frac{q_1^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] = \int_{-q_0/2}^{q_0/2} \int_{-q_0/2}^{q_0/2} \frac{1}{q_0^2} \frac{q_1^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} dq_1 dq_2$$

Integrating and simplifying results in

$$E \left[\frac{q_1^2}{(-2b + q_2 - q_1)^2} \right] = \frac{1}{q_0^2} \left\{ q_0^2 + 4b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) + \frac{q_0^2}{4} \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) + 2q_0 b \ln \left(\frac{2b - q_0}{2b + q_0} \right) \right\} \quad (37)$$

Therefore, combining the results of Equations 35, 36 and 37 provides the final expression for the variance given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) = T_s^2 \cdot \left\{ -\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{q_0^2} \left\{ b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) - q_0 b \ln \left(\frac{2b - q_0}{2b + q_0} \right) - 4b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) + q_0^2 + 4b^2 \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) + \frac{q_0^2}{4} \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) + 2q_0 b \ln \left(\frac{2b - q_0}{2b + q_0} \right) \right\} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

which reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \text{var}(\epsilon) = T_s^2 \cdot \left\{ 3/4 + b/q_0 \ln \left(\frac{2b - q_0}{2b + q_0} \right) + (b^2/q_0^2 + 1/4) \ln \left(\frac{4b^2}{4b^2 - q_0^2} \right) \right\} \quad (38) \end{aligned}$$

It can be shown using l'Hôpital's rule that

$$\lim_{q_0 \rightarrow 0} \text{var}(\epsilon) = 0$$

as would be expected.

3 Conclusions

We have now examined three principal sources of error in estimating the zero-crossings of uniformly sampled data using linear interpolation. As shown by Equations 7, 16, 28 and 34, the mean error due to linear interpolation, additive white Gaussian noise, and quantization, each taken separately, is zero. Derivation of the variance of the error for each of these three effects leads to Equations 11, 24, 29, and 38, with Equations 11 and 24 representing the error due to linear interpolation for sampling at the Nyquist rate, and for sampling at greater than the Nyquist rate, respectively. Though the probability distributions of the error have not been developed, for a large number of zero-crossing estimates, we can apply the central limit theorem, and therefore expect the error distribution to be nearly zero-mean Gaussian (with variance as determined here). Therefore, in signal processing applications which

may want to take advantage of both zero-crossing and uniform-sampling (digital signal processing) techniques, these results may prove useful in determining the acceptable levels of error as a function of sampling rate, noise level, and quantization.

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